

Active Learning in the development of Product Data Management competences in an Industrial Engineering and Management Master Program

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060883>

Abstract

Product Data Management (PDM) is a crucial function within the Manufacturing Planning and Control area, as it should provide reliable information for the other functions of that area. Thus, the development of PDM competences in Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) programs is a matter of utmost importance, especially given that more and more companies must deal with high product diversity and customisation. Furthermore, today's Industry 4.0 context has led to a dramatic increase in the amount of information on products and functionalities inherent to Smart Factories, emphasizing even more the PDM importance. The objective of this paper is to describe and analyse the PDM teaching approach adopted in 2022/23 by the teachers of the Production Information System course unit of the IEM Master Program at University of Minho, in terms of technical and transversal competences development. The course unit consists of two parts, both incorporating active learning elements. The first part is about PDM fundamentals and uses a mix of expository teaching, think-pair-share, and hands-on activities. Right from the start, students are confronted with real industrial scenarios and must incrementally develop the corresponding PDM models. The second part consists of a team project (project-based learning, learning-by-doing). Each team selects a real product family and develops its PDM model by hand (using a proprietary graphic language). Then, using proprietary software, each team implements and demonstrates the correctness of its solution. In terms of findings, the students' marks (encompassing an individual test and project report/presentation/discussion) revealed a good level of competences development, both technical (mainly) and transversal. Informal feedback from students highlighted some limitations but was clearly positive. The institutional assessment report validated this perception by showing that the students rated as good both the pedagogical dimension of the course unit and the motivation to face the challenges set for them.

Keywords: Engineering Education; Active Learning; Project Approaches; Product Data Management; Manufacturing Planning and Control.

1 Introduction

Industrial organizations have been facing technological and organizational challenges related to the large number of different and customized products that they have to deal with since the ability to manufacture a large diversity of products is now a requirement for a large number of organizations (Martins et al., 2021).

Product Data Management (PDM) is the area of Manufacturing Planning and Control that represents, integrates, and manages the data about the products, from conception to manufacturing. It includes data about the engineering drawings, projects, product technical specifications, bill of materials, bill of operations, machine programs or instructions, among others (Liu & Xu, 2001; Martins et al., 2021; Sousa et al., 2009).

The ability to deal efficiently with a high diversity and customization of products in manufacturing systems depends significantly on the product data model used to represent each product and provide information to the manufacturing planning and control processes. Some authors, such as Gao, Aziz, Maropoulos, & Cheung (2003), believe that PDM is the most important area within an organization or system. They call attention to the level of efficiency required to manage product data and argue that it has been increasing due to the need

to launch new products to the market as quickly as possible, even more in the actual context of Industry 4.0, since the quantity of information and functionalities increased to implement Smart Factories (Guo et al., 2022).

Given the relevance of this subject, the Department of Production and Systems (DPS) of the School of Engineering of the University of Minho (UM), in Portugal, has carried out several research and development projects in this field and developed a new generic product data model called GenPDM (Generic PDM). GenPDM is a “flexible and easy to use” model capable to automatically generate information about each product - including information to characterize the product, its bill of materials, bill of operations and all remaining information required by different processes implemented in the organization. The information of each product is generated based on generic structures and rules defined by users of each organization, for each product family (Gomes et al., 2009; Martins & Sousa, 2013).

The Industrial Engineering and Management Master Program (MEGI) is a two-year master’s degree program of UM and one of the main courses in the DPS. The 2nd semester of the 1st year has 6 courses units, among which Production Information Systems (PIS). The PIS course unit aims to develop Product Data Management competences in MEGI students. The PIS syllabus includes the presentation and teaching of different product data models, in particular the GenPDM model (University of Minho, 2024).

Research in engineering education was shown the effectiveness of active learning and project-based learning (PBL) approaches to improve student’s learning ability in different subject matters and to develop transversal competences of project management, autonomy and communication (Christie & Graaff, 2016; P. Guo et al., 2020; Lima et al., 2007; Powell et al., 2003), making these approaches popular in engineering education (Kolmos, A., & De Graaff, 2014; Sousa et al., 2023). Over time, several examples can be identified in engineering education of different learning approaches and practices worldwide, as published in the MIT report ‘The Global state of the art in engineering education’ (Graham, 2018).

Over the last two decades, DPS also has been applying and testing several active learning and PBL approaches in its main Industrial Engineering and Management (EGI) programs, in different curricular years and course units, where each approach has its own characteristics (Sousa et al., 2023). An example refers to the PIS course unit since the teachers applies active learning principles to develop student’s Product Data Management competences for their professional lives. The application of these principles in PIS is particularly important because most of the program contents refer to generic concepts and tools that are not easily understood if they are not applied by the students.

The aim of this paper is to describe and analyse the teaching approach, from a conceptual and operational point of view, adopted by the teachers of the PIS course unit in the academic year 2022/2023.

The paper is structured in five sections. Section 2 presents the methods used to carry out this work. Section 3 presents and describes the teaching approach applied in the PIS course unit. Section 4 discusses the main results and limitations of the adopted approach. Section 5 presents the final remarks of the paper.

2 Methods

The development of this paper considered the official document describing the PIS course unit and the respective institutional assessment reports. The official document identifies the most relevant information of the course unit, namely general information (such as the course unit designation, main scientific area or number of hours), key learning outcomes, program summary, bibliography, teaching methods and assessment model. The institutional report provides information about the overall satisfaction level of the students. Furthermore, the analysis of the teaching approach (section 3) and discussion (section 4) was led by the teachers of the

course unit with the support of the remaining authors, and taking into consideration the feedback given by the students (feedback collected informally throughout the course unit).

The teaching approach described in the next section has been applied in the PIS course unit for the last 10 years, not only in the MEGI Master Program but also in the Engineering and Operations Management Master Program (MEGO). Over the last years, some adjustments and changes have been introduced to improve the outcomes of the course unit. This paper describes the teaching experience during the academic year 2022/2023 (the last edition considering the date of this paper) in the MEGI Master Program as it is the main course of DPS (however, the teaching approach and results are similar at MEGO Master Program). Every academic year the project is planned by the coordination team shortly before the course unit classes start to define conceptual and operational aspects, objectives and schedule important dates (milestones, deliverables, etc.).

The characterization and analysis of the teaching approach applied considers the following parameters: (i) number of ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System), (ii) duration, (iii) curricular year, (iv) different teaching methods of the course unit, (v) number of projects with an industrial organization involved, (vi) numbers of students involved, (vii) number and size of teams, (viii) size and role of the teachers, (xii) premises of the project, (xiii) number and type of milestones, (xiv) number and type of deliverables, (xv) assessment model and (xvi) students satisfaction level. The information of the last parameter was mostly gathered from the feedback collected and institutional assessment reports.

3 Analysis of the Teaching Approach

This section describes and analyses the PIS course unit, according to the parameters defined in the previous section. Furthermore, it addresses other information, namely technical and transversal competences developed during the course unit.

The PIS course unit is integrated in the 2nd semester of the 1st year of the MEGI Master Program. The PIS's main scientific area is Industrial and Systems Engineering, and (i) holds five ECTS, (ii) lasts one semester, and (iii) has 45 hours of classes and 95 hours of autonomous work. All classes are presential. In the academic year of 2022/2023, from mid-February 2022 to May 2023, 49 students were registered in the PIS course unit.

The teaching approach applied in the development of Product Data Management competences in the PIS course unit considered two main parts. The first part consisted of a set of seven theoretical and seven theoretical-practical two-hour classes, over seven consecutive weeks. In the first part, the main contents of the course unit were presented. In the theoretical-practical classes, a set of real case studies from different industries was selected to apply the knowledge gathered. The case studies selected were shoes, wood cabinets, metal pipes and concrete beams. This part considered a more traditional and expository teaching approach, even though some active learning principles were used in the case study discussions, such as Think-Pair-Share (e.g. about product diversity / customization and PDM role) or Hands-on (e.g. students were provided with a real product – an electric lantern – so they could disassemble it and create the respective bill of materials and bill of operations). At the end of the first part, students were assessed based on an individual written test.

The second part of the part of the course unit was a project, which constitutes the main focus of this paper. The main objective of the project, in terms of technical competences, was to represent from scratch a family of products with the GenPDM concepts and tools presented in the first part of the course unit.

The project last eight weeks and has four main stages (Figure 1). The moments marked in the figure are not intended to constitute rigid dates for the completion of each phase, serving mainly for students' teams to

understand what is expected in each phase and to be able to monitor their progress. In fact, at certain times, different teams may not even be at the same stage of the project.

Figure 1. Phases of the Project

Students had four hours of weekly contact sessions, organized by team meetings and where the teachers supervised and supported the execution of the project. Additional support was also provided outside these periods, especially through presential and online meetings with each group. In the academic year of 2022/2023, the coordination team of the project was composed of the two teachers of the course unit.

The following paragraphs describe each stage and the assessment model of the project.

Stage 1: Teams formation and definition of team-specific product family

In the first stage of the project, the students organized themselves into seven teams of five or six students (each team could have a maximum of six students). Of the 49 students registered in the course unit, only 41 carried out the project (eight students were in Erasmus mobility).

After that, each team started working in its project. The first task for each team was to define a specific product family to represent and the set of options (diversity) that would be considered in the product family. This stage is particularly important since it influences the way how the remaining tasks of the project will be carried out, and also the complexity of executing them. The following guidelines were given by the teachers:

- Try to choose an example of an industrial organization where the team could have access to the needed information. Alternatively, each team could select freely an example but that can make access to accurate information more difficult; for instance, it is simpler to collect the customization options of a particular product family of an industrial organization than to identify which customization options make sense (with no actual real context). Moreover, all projects that are carried out in partnership with industrial organizations are always a good opportunity for both students and companies to share knowledge. In the edition under study, four of the seven teams developed the project using examples provided by industrial organizations, namely cardboard boxes, cabinets, electrical walls and flatware.
- Avoid large project scopes. The objective of the project is to evaluate the ability of each team to apply the concepts and tools learned in the course unit, so they should focus on simple and single examples for each point instead of complex and multi-examples applying the same concept or tool.

Besides that, students were also advised to define quickly the project scope in order to avoid delays in the remaining tasks of the project, and, consequently, extra working time outside of class hours. This stage took between one to two weeks.

Stage 2: Model Development (by hand)

The second stage consisted of the development of a model to represent the product family and customization options defined in the previous stage, using the GenPDM concepts and tools. GenPDM includes a graphical representation language that was used by students to represent each model. Figure 2 shows a Product Data Model for cardboard boxes developed by students.

Each team started this stage once the product family was defined and each team should have the model defined until week 5 of the project. The role of the teachers during this period was to give technical support and clarify doubts of each group, and not to support the management of each team.

Figure 2. Example of a Product Data Model for cardboard boxes developed by students

Stage 3: Model Implementation (in proprietary software)

The third stage consisted of implementing the model (defined in the previous stage) in a specific software, the Smart Manufacturing System (SMS) software. This software used in this stage was developed at DPS-UM and that uses the GenPDM concepts and tools to represent all information about products. Besides PDM, the SMS software has more functional areas and processes implemented that require a huge amount of information. Figure 3 shows an example of the software interface with the Product Data Model of cardboard boxes.

This stage started at week 5 and took until week 7; therefore each team had a quite short time to represent their model in the software (it was their first contact with the software and there was little documentation available). To overcome this issue, at week 4 the software was installed on one computer of each group, and three hours of training program to all students on how to use the software were provided. During the training program, all teams followed the representation of a GenPDM model in the software, considering as an example a family of sport shoes (as this example has already been used in the first part of the course unit). This session applied a hands-on-learning approach since students were watching the representation of the model in the software and, at the same time, replicating the same sequence of steps on their computers.

After that, each team started the implementation of their own case studies in the software. At the end of week 7, all teams had to send the software database (project deliverable 1).

Figure 3. Example of the software interface with the Product Data Model of cardboard boxes

Stage 4: Presentation, Report and Demonstration of Planning and Control Outcomes

In the final week of the project (week 8), each team did a ten minute presentation to the remaining colleagues and teachers. Students were requested to present their models, the main novelties and limitations of their solution and the major difficulties during the project. Each presentation was followed by a five minutes discussion where at least one question was requested from each team, in addition to questions from the teachers. At the end of the day, each team had to send the document used for the presentation (project deliverable 2).

Additionally (also at the end of week 8) each team had to prepare and send a written report (project deliverable 3). In this report, students had to present their models and critically review the entire process, namely identifying the novelties, limitations, and restrictions, not only of their model, but also regarding the GenPDM model and the SMS software. A template for the report has not been provided, but the teachers encouraged students to deliver concise and short reports.

As referred previously, a PDM model should provide all information required for the manufacturing planning and control processes. Therefore, in stage 4, the teachers used one of the case studies developed by the students, to show, in the SMS software, the impact of that model in the outcomes on the manufacturing planning and control processes. That is the reason why the database (project deliverable 1) was sent one week before the remaining deliverables (to give teachers time to prepare for this session).

Figure 4 shows some examples of SMS software interfaces based on the Product Data Model of cardboard boxes. Figure 4(a) shows the purchase orders suggested by the SMS software to satisfy all customer orders defined in the system. Figure 4(b) shows the capacity requirements to satisfy the customer orders. Figure 4(c) shows the interface of a manager/planner that includes all information of each manufacturing batch (e.g. components needed, operations and their status). Figure 4(d) shows the interface to be installed in a workstation and that displays all information required to execute each job (e.g. information about the product to be manufactured, operation, quantity).

This session was presented by the teacher after all team presentations and took approximately one hour. It is important to note that although students did not have an active role in the preparation of this session, they had the opportunity to see and understand the impact of their models (and the decisions they made throughout the previous stages) on the outcomes presented. Moreover, students have also the opportunity to

see the application of some methods and algorithms that have been learned in other course units, such as Manufacturing Planning and Control (a course unit of the Bachelor in Industrial Engineering and Management).

Figure 4. Examples of SMS software interfaces in different manufacturing planning and control processes, based on the Product Data Model of cardboard boxes

Assessment Model

The assessment model of the PIS course unit considers both parts. The first part is evaluated by an individual written test and the second part, that is, the project, is assessed based on: (i) the database that results from stage 3 (project deliverable 1); (ii) the presentation and discussion of stage 4 (project deliverable 2); (iii) the written report of stage 4 (project deliverable 3). There is no peer assessment to distinguish, within each team, individual performance in the project, but its application in future editions is being discussed.

The weights assigned to each item have been changing over time. In the edition under study, the written test counted 65% and the project counted 35% (database – 10%, presentation – 10% and report – 15%). The assessment considered different criteria such as technical issues, structure of each document, communication/writing skills, creativity, among others. The average score of the all-individual tests was 77% and for all-team projects was 78%.

4 Discussion

This section presents a critical review of the: (i) teaching approach applied, (ii) feedback gathered informally from the students, and (iii) results of the course unit institutional assessment reports.

The students' feedback gathered informally throughout the course unit was positive, but to collect more detailed feedback, there was a 30-minute session at the end of the project where all teams were invited to share their opinions and new ideas about the course unit. The students referred repeatedly that the project

was very important to learn the contents of the course unit and helped them to understand the potential for industrial organizations of the concepts and tools learned. Besides that, they also mention that the project helped them to recognize the importance of product data in the outcomes of manufacturing planning and control processes.

On the other hand, students also called attention to the high number of deliverables of the course unit and suggested that the SMS software could be installed on the computer of all students (instead of just one per team) to allow all students to participate and work in parallel. The teachers explained that the SMS software was installed in just one computer to avoid problems managing the database of each team (since the software database is designed to be stored in a data centre where several users could be linked, but it is not possible to implement a similar technological infrastructure in the university).

The institutional assessment reports of the course unit also showed interesting results. At the end of each semester, students are requested to reply to a quick questionnaire about how each course unit worked. The questionnaire of the PIS course unit was replied to by 27 students and the results are shown in Figure 5. The institutional assessment report shows that the assessment of the teaching dimension of the course unit was very good (4.2 out of 5 points; 84%). The motivation of each student to deal with the challenges they have to face, namely the project, was also very good (4 out of 5 points; 80%). All four dimensions improved compared to the previous year. Finally, the students' average grade in the curricular unit was 78% (15.5 out of 20; individual test and project), also demonstrating the success of the approach applied.

Figure 5. Results of the institutional assessment reports (PIS course unit; MEGI master's degree, 2022/2023 academic year)

5 Conclusion

This paper describes the active learning approach applied in the PIS course unit of the Master's in Industrial Engineering and Management (MEGI) at University of Minho, which has been developed and improved over the last few years, based on the particularities of the educational context of the course unit. The approach adopted presents good results both in the development of technical and transversal competences and in students' satisfaction. Particularly, the development of Product Data Management competences allows students to go deeper into the concepts and tools proposed which will be important for their professional careers.

To support the results of this study, future editions of the PIS course unit should collect more qualitative and quantitative evidence about their strengths and weaknesses, which may lead to improvement in the conceptual and operational aspects of the active learning approach applied.

Finally, it is important to note that the active learning approach described in this paper has been considered efficient over time in this course unit due to ongoing research on active learning, project-based learning and

Product Data Management carried out in the department of the faculty (either in the development of new models and software). The implementation of a similar approach in other educational environments may lead to different challenges that should be analysed carefully.

Acknowledgement

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020. The authors would like to acknowledge all the companies and students that participated in this pedagogical experience.

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